

A Study to Assess the Knowledge Regarding Handling of Children with Emotional and Behaviour Problem in order to Prepare a Self Instruction Module among the Selected Primary School Teachers in Bangalore South

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Abstract: Mental health is a critical component of children learning and general health. Fostering social and emotional health in children as a part of healthy child development must therefore National priority both the promotion of mental health in children and the treatment of mental disorders should be major public health goals [1]. Childhood mental health problems are associated with significant adverse health and psychosocial outcomes in adulthood like antisocial or delinquent behavior, depression suicide etc. and impose a substantial burden on the community. Good mental health is characterized by satisfactory emotional, social and behavioral functioning. This is reflected by positive feelings about oneself and ability to interact well with others and meet the demands routines of everyday life [2]. This study attempts to “Assess the knowledge regarding handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem in order to prepare a self-instructional module among primary school teachers of Bangalore south” [3]. To assess the level of knowledge of primary school teachers regarding handling of children with emotional and behavioral problems with their selected demographic variables [4]. **Methods:** The research design selected for this study was descriptive research design. The sample comprised of 30 Primary school teachers of Bangalore south. Convenient sampling technique was used to draw the sample for the study. The tool developed and used was structured questionnaire. Experts validated the content validity of the tool was found to be reliable and feasible. Collected data as analyzed and then presented in the form of tables, graphs and charts. The results were described by using descriptive and inferential statistics. **Results:** Majority 36% primary school teachers belong to age group 40-49, similarly 30% of primary school teachers in age group of 20-29 followed by 23.3% in 30-39 and 10% in 50-59. Majority 93.3% primary school teachers are female and rest 6.7% primary school teachers are male. 63.3% primary school teachers are under graduate and 36.75% are post graduate. 90% of primary school teachers are married and rest 10% are married. Majority 60% primary school teachers belong to nuclear family, 33.3% belong to joint and rest 6.7% belong to single. 63.3% majority of the primary school teachers had family monthly income of below Rs. 25, 000, 16.7% primary school teachers had monthly family income between RS. 25,000-50,000 and 20% of primary school teachers had family monthly income Rs.50, 000-1, 00,000. Majority 83.3% primary school teachers had sources of information on emotional and behavioral problems through electronic media and 16.7% had sources of information through print media. The findings of the study revealed that there was significant association of knowledge scores of primary school teachers with demographic variables of educational status, source of knowledge and marital status.

Introduction

Children are mirror of a nation. They are our future and our most precious resources. The quality of tomorrow's world and perhaps even its survival will be determined by the well-being, safety and the physical and intellectual development of children today [5]. To predict the future of a nation, it has been remarked, one need not consult the stars; it can more easily and plainly be read in the faces of its children. According to World Health Report 15 % of children have serious emotional disturbance. Epidemiological study of child and adolescent psychiatric disorders conducted by ICMR indicated the overall prevalence of mental and behavioral disorders in Indian children to be 12.5%. Mental disorders account for 5 of the top 10 leading causes of disability in the world for children above 5 years of age [6]. Besides the increase in number of children seeking help for emotional problems, over the years, the type of problems has also undergone a tremendous change. Indian studies also reflect similar variability [7]. Studies conducted in rural and urban areas of different part of India suggest prevalence range ranging from approximately 1.16 % to 43.1%. School teacher is the second mother to every child. So children listen to every point that teacher teaches, the unhealthy child cannot be expected to take full advantage of schooling Health education must remain mainly in the hands of the teacher and the school health Workers. Health education is a part of general education [8].

A growing understanding of the Physical, mental, emotional and normal nature of the children is the essence of professional teaching ability. Emotional behavioral problems are widely prevalence in any school children. Teacher can have an immense impact on young children's health as reported by UNESCO; there are almost 43 million teachers around the world at the primary and secondary level. Every day at least 5-6 hrs [9]. It is the school teacher who comes in contact with school children. If school teacher have knowledge regarding emotional and behavioral problems it will help the teachers to identify problems as early as possible and take remedial measures promptly. Care of school age child is not only important in itself, the school system also offers an excellent country wide network and entry point for a comprehensive health program. The quality of human resources of any country is largely determined by the quality of its child development services. The etiological factors for mental health problems of children are usually biological risk factors, genetic risk factors, family relationship risks, experiential risks and social environmental risk factors [10].

A number of specific biological factors are associated with behavioral and developmental problems, mainly they contribute to behavioral & emotional problems. Teachers plays very important role in early diagnosis of mental health problems, giving reference to medical personal and also promotion of mental health among children in their schools. Schools children will spend their more time with their respective school teachers. School plays a crucial and formative role in the spheres of cognitive, language, emotional, social and moral development of children. There is now a growing recognition that schools have a significant role in promoting mental health. Teachers are powerful groups who have in their process of education studied the nature of individual growth. This has equipped them to be in a position to shape and reshape behaviors that are warranted [11].

Nearly one in five children and adolescents will have emotional and behavioral disorders at some times in their youth. Mental disorders in schools amount to 3.12 % in students. Even by conservative estimates 10% of the child population suffers from mental disturbances with serious associated impairments including learning problems, health problems and during abuse any given time. At least 3% of school age children suffer from serious emotional disturbances at any given point of time. The quality of childhood life solely depends on the type of environment. School and neighborhood unhealthy social surroundings can put them at stress and can increase their vulnerability to develop emotional disorders [12]. As children are easily amenable to different stresses and strain, it is imperative on the part of parent and teachers to know the intricacies of a healthy psychosocial environment leading to behavioral patterns which are personally satisfying and socially acceptable. Schools have an unprecedented opportunity to improve the lives of young people with nations moving towards a commitment to universal education. Schools are finding it necessary to expand

their roles by providing health services to deal with factors. interfering with schooling. The years of primary, secondary and high school education become increasing burden and stressful with various languages that have to be learnt and an increasingly heavy load of syllabus [13]. There is a growing recognition that schools may play a significant role in producing psychopathology, especially due to the formative influences of school as normal as well as pathological development. It therefore become imperative to view the school's system from the perspectives of primary, secondary and tertiary prevention with reference to the child's mental health [14].

Teachers have an immense impact on young children's mental health. They enjoy a very important position in the formation of healthy mind in then as reported by UNESCO. There are almost 43 million teachers around the world at the primary and secondary levels. The size alone of the teacher population is of public health significance. It is in this context the importance of a teacher becomes vital in safeguarding the mental health of children [15]. This is especially true in the case of Indian situation where there is considerable shortage of mental health facilities for children. Teacher's perception is essential in planning and implementing like skill education, mental health education, psycho social intervention and professional referral when necessary [16]. Teachers have been utilized for school health programs in health status assessment and health education. Since there is considerable shortage at mental health professionals, schools teachers can make important contributions in the promotion of mental health of children [17]. The opportunity that teachers have for interpersonal relationship greatly contribute to the mental health of children [18].

Methodology

The descriptive design was used to assess the knowledge of primary school teachers regarding handling of children's with emotional and behavioral problem in selected primary schools of Bangalore south. The study subjects were selected from primary schools of Bangalore south. The target population for the present study was primary school teachers of Bangalore south. A sample consists of primary school teachers above the age group of 20 and below 60 (male & female) at selected primary schools of Bangalore south. The sample size comprises of 30 primary school teachers. The convenient sampling type was adopted for selecting samples for the present study.

Results

Table 1. Distribution of respondents by demographic variables (N=30)

Characteristics	Category	Primary school teachers	
		Frequency	Percent
Age Group	20-29	9	30.0
	30-39	7	23.3
	40-49	11	36.7
	50-59	3	10.0
Gender	Male	2	6.7
	Female	28	93.3
Educational status	Undergraduate	19	63.3
	Post graduate	11	36.7
Marital Status	Bachelor/spinster	3	10.0
	Married	27	90.0
Type of family	Joint	10	33.3
	Nuclear	18	60.0
	Single	2	6.7
Family income per month	Below 25,000	19	63.3
	25,000-50,000	5	16.7
	50,000-1,00,000	6	20.0
Sources of information	Print media	5	16.7
	Electronic media	25	83.3

Table 1 gives a description of classification of primary school teachers by age and gender. Out of 30 primary school teachers 30.0% (9) of the teachers are in the age of 20-29 years, 23.3% (7) of the teachers are in between the age of 30-39 years, 36.7%(11) of the teachers are in between the age of 40-49 years, whereas 10.0%(3) of the teachers are in between the age of 50-55 years. Out of 30 primary school teachers 6.7% (2) of the teachers were males as compared to 93.3% (28) of female primary school teachers. Out of 30 primary school teachers 63.3 % (19) of the primary school teachers are undergraduate, 36.75% (11) of the primary school teachers are post graduate. Out of 30 primary school teachers 10% (3) primary school teachers are bachelor whereas 90.0% (27) of the primary school teachers are married. Out of 30 primary school teachers 33.3% (10) of the primary school teachers were from joint family, 60.0% (18) were from nuclear family followed by 6.7 % (2) primary school teachers live single. Out of 30 primary school teacher 63.3% (19) of the primary school teacher had family monthly income of below 25,000 Rs. 16.7% (5) primary school teacher had monthly family income between 25,000-50,000 and 20.0% (6) primary school teacher had family monthly income 50,000-1,00,000. Further out of 30 primary school teachers majority 83.3% (25) of the primary school teacher had source of information on emotional and behavioral problem in primary school children through electronic media and 16.7% (5) teacher had source of information through print media.

Table 2. Classification of primary school teachers by overall knowledge level on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problems.

Knowledge Level	Category	Respondents	
		Number	Percent (%)
Inadequate	<34% score	7	23.33
Moderate	34%-67% score	19	63.33
Adequate	67%-100% score	4	13.3
Total		30	100.0

Table 2 depicts classification of primary school teachers by knowledge level on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problems. It represents that out of 30 primary school teachers 13.3(4)% of the primary school teacher had adequate knowledge, 63.33(19) % of the primary school teachers had moderate knowledge and 23.3(7)% of the primary school teacher had inadequate knowledge on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problems. The total mean knowledge score was found to be 67.09% with SD of 40.56% on general question and handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem. The aspect wise mean knowledge score of primary school teacher was ranged between 13.7 % and 1.40 %. The highest (54.8%) mean knowledge score was found in the aspect of general questions of emotional and behavioral problems followed by knowledge of teachers in handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem (28 %).

Table 3. Over all and aspect wise mean knowledge scores of primary school teachers on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problems

S.No.	Knowledge aspects	Respondents Knowledge					
		Statements	Max. Score	Mean	SD	Mean n(%)	SD (%)
1	General questions on emotional and behavioral problems	25	20	13.7	4.59	54.8%	41.55
2	Knowledge of teachers in handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem	05	05	1.40	1.35	28	38.96
	Over All	30	25	15.1	5.94	67.09	40.56

Table 3 shows overall mean knowledge of primary school teachers on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem. The overall mean knowledge score of primary school teachers on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem was found to be 67.09% and SD as 40.56 %.

Table 4. Association between age group and knowledge level of primary schoolteachers, on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem

Age in Years	Sample (N)	Knowledge Level						X ² Value
		Adequate		Moderate		Inadequate		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	
20-29	9	1	11.1	7	77.7	1	11.1	3.69 ^{NS}
30-39	7	1	14.2	4	57.1	2	28.5	
40-49	11	2	18.1	6	54.5	3	27.2	
50-59	3	0	0	2	66.6	1	33.3	
Total	30	4		19		7		

NS- Not Significant at 5% level; X² (0.05, 4df) = 9.49

It shows that among 30 primary school teacher in the age group of 20-30 years, 11.1 % (1) had adequate knowledge level , 77.7 % (7) respondent had moderate knowledge level and 1.1%(1) respondents had inadequate knowledge level. Further, among 7 primary school teacher between the age group 30-39 years, 14.2 % (1) had adequate knowledge level, 57.1 % (4) had moderate knowledge level and 28.5% (2) had inadequate knowledge level. Also among 11 respondents with the age group 40-49 years, 18.1 % (2) had adequate knowledge level, 54.54 % (6) had moderate knowledge level and 27.2 (3) had inadequate knowledge level. And among 3 respondents with the age group 50-59 years, 0 % (0) had adequate knowledge level, 66.6% (2) had moderate knowledge level and 33.3 (1) had inadequate knowledge level.

Hence, the value of X² is found to be not significant at 5% level (X² = 3.69*, P>0.05). It indicates that there is no significant association between knowledge and the respondent’s age.

Table 5. Association between gender and knowledge level of primary school teacher on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem

Gender	Sample (N)	Knowledge Level						X ² Value
		Adequate		Moderate		Inadequate		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	
Male	2	0	0	1	50	1	50	0.25 ^{NS}
Female	28	4	14.2	18	64.2	6	21.4	
Total	30	4		19		7		

NS- Not Significant at 5% level; X² (0.05, 2 df) = 5.99

It indicates the association between gender and knowledge level of primary school teacher on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem. Among 2 male respondents 0% (0) respondents were found to be having adequate knowledge level, 50% (1) respondents possessed moderate knowledge level and 50%(1) primary school teacher had inadequate knowledge and among 28 female primary school teachers 14.2 % (4) female primary school teacher possessed adequate knowledge, 64.2%(18) primary school teachers had moderate knowledge and 21.4% (6) female primary school teacher found to have inadequate knowledge.

Hence, the value of X² is found to be not significant at 5% level (X² = 0.25, P>0.05). It indicates that there is no significant association between knowledge and the respondent’s gender.

Table 6. Association between educational status and knowledge level of primary school teachers on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem

Educational Status	Sample (N)	Knowledge Level						X ² Value
		Adequate		Moderate		Inadequate		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	
University graduate	19	1	2.4	13	68.4	5	26.3	19.2*
Post graduate	11	3	27.2	6	54.4	2	18.1	
Total	30	4		19		7		

*Significant at 5% level; X² (0.05, 10 df) = 18.31

Table 6 depicts the association between education and knowledge level of primary school teachers on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem. Among 19 primary school teachers qualified with university graduate, 2.4 % (1) had adequate knowledge, 68.4 % (13) had moderate knowledge and 26.3 % (5) had inadequate knowledge. Among 11 primary school teachers qualifies with post graduate, 27.2% (3) had adequate knowledge level, 54.4 % (6) primary school teacher had moderate knowledge level and 18.1% (2) had inadequate knowledge. Hence, the value of X² is found to be significant at 5% level (X² = 19.2* P<0.05). It indicates that there is significant association between knowledge and the primary school teacher education.

Table 7. Association between marital status and knowledge level of primary school teachers on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem

Marital Status	Sample (N)	Knowledge Level						X ² Value
		Adequate		Moderate		Inadequate		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	
Unmarried	3	0	0	3	100	0	0	0.76 ^{NS}
Married	27	4	14.8	16	59.2	7	25.9	
Total	30	4		19		7		

NS: Not Significant at 5% level; X² (0.05, 2 df) = 5.99

Table 7 depicts Association between marital status and knowledge level of primary school teachers on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem. Among 3 unmarried primary school teacher 0 % (0) primary school teacher were found to be having adequate knowledge level, 100 % (3) of unmarried primary school teacher possessed moderate knowledge level and 0% (0) of unmarried primary school teachers possessed inadequate. Further among 27 married primary school teachers 14.8 % (4) primary school teacher who possessed adequate knowledge while 59.2 % (16) of married primary school teacher found to have moderate knowledge and 25.9% (7) of married primary school teacher possessed inadequate. Hence, the value of X² is found to be not significant at 5% level (X² = 4.38* P>0.05). It indicates that there is no significant association between knowledge and the respondent's marital status.

Table 8. Association between type of family and knowledge level of primary school teachers on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problems

Type of Family	Sample (N)	Knowledge Level						X ² Value
		Adequate		Moderate		Inadequate		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	
Joint	10	2	20	3	30	5	50	0.05 ^{NS}
Nuclear	18	2	11.1	14	77.7	2	11.1	
Single	2	0	0	2	100	0	0	
Total	30	4		19		7		

NS: Non-Significant at 5% level; X² (0.05, 2 df) = 5.99

Table 8 shows Association between type of family and knowledge level of primary school teachers on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problems. Among 10 primary school teachers from joint family, 20% (2) had adequate knowledge level, 30 % (3) had moderate knowledge level and 50% (5) had inadequate knowledge level. Further among 18 respondents from nuclear family 11.1% (2) had adequate knowledge level, 77.7 % (14) had moderate knowledge level and 11.1% (2) had inadequate knowledge level. And 2 primary school teachers from single family, 0 % (0) had adequate knowledge, 100% (2) had moderate knowledge and 0 % (0) had inadequate knowledge. Hence, the value of X^2 is found to be non-significant at 5% level ($X^2 = 0.168^{NS}$, $P > 0.05$). It indicates that there is no significant association between knowledge and the respondent's type of family.

Table 9. Association between family monthly income and knowledge level of primary school teachers on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem

Family monthly income	Sample (N)	Knowledge Level						X ² Value
		Adequate		Moderate		Inadequate		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	
Below Rs.25000	19	2	10.5	10	52.6	7	36.8	7.78 ^{NS}
Rs.25,000-50,000	5	0	0	5	100	0	0	
Rs.50,000-1,00,000	6	2	33.3	4	66.6	0	0	
Total	30	4		19		7		

NS- Not Significant at 5% level; $X^2 (0.05, 6 \text{ df}) = 12.59$

Table 9 shows the association between family monthly income and knowledge level of primary school teachers on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problems. It shows that among 19 primary school teachers with family income below Rs. 25000, 10.5% (2) had adequate knowledge level while 52.6 % (10) had moderate knowledge level and 36.8% (7) had inadequate knowledge level. among 5 primary school teachers with family income between 25,000- 50,000, 0% (0) had adequate knowledge level while 100 % (5) had moderate knowledge level and 0% (0) had inadequate knowledge level, among 6 primary school teachers with family income between 50,000-1,00,000, 33.3% (2) had adequate knowledge level while, 84.2 % (5) had moderate knowledge level and 2.6% (1) had inadequate knowledge level.

Further, among 14 respondents with family income above 15000, 21.4% (3) respondents had adequate knowledge level and 66.6% (4) had moderate knowledge level and 0 % (0) had inadequate knowledge level. Hence, the value of X^2 is found to be not significant at 5% level ($X^2 = 3.89^*$, $P > 0.05$). It indicates that there is no significant association between knowledge and the respondent's income.

Table 10. Association between source of information and knowledge level of primary school teacher on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem.

Source of information	Sample (N)	Knowledge Level						X ² Value
		Adequate		Moderate		Inadequate		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	
Print media	5	2	40	1	20	2	40	0.76 ^{NS}
Electronic media	25	2	8	18	72	5	20	
Total	30	4		19		7		

NS: Not Significant at 5% level; $X^2 (0.05, 2 \text{ df}) = 5.99$

Table 10 depicts Association between source of information and knowledge level of primary school teachers on handling of children with emotional and behavioral problem. Among 5 primary school teacher responding to print media 40 % (2) primary school teachers were found to be having adequate knowledge level, 20 % (1) primary school teacher possessed moderate knowledge level and 40%(2) primary school teacher possessed inadequate. Further among 25 primary school teacher responding electronic media 8 % (2) primary school teacher possessed adequate knowledge while 72 % (18) of primary school teacher found to have moderate knowledge and 20%(5) primary school teacher possessed inadequate. Hence, the value of X^2 is found to be not significant at 5% level ($X^2 = 4.38^* P > 0.05$). It indicates that there is no significant association between knowledge and the respondent's marital status.

Conclusion

The study concluded the need of educating the primary school teacher in handling the children with emotional and behavioral problem so that every aspects of the child development is considered and taken care. The information booklet which is provided to them will also help them to gain some knowledge.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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